

ABOUT THE CLASSIFICATION OF KINSHIP TERMS

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Abstract:

This article examines various approaches to the study of kinship terms in the English and Uzbek languages, along with the criteria used for selecting and classifying them. A person's status in society, social relationships, and behavior are all influenced by their kinship. The national mindset is defined by the terminology kinship attributes, which also reflect the distinctiveness of the language and the specifics of the national course.

Key words: kinship, classification, relatives, terminology, terms, relations

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Introduction

Every language has a vocabulary for describing the relationships between a person and their relatives. These are regarded as terms of kinship. Their characteristics are categorized as internal laws since they represent the linguistic array's features as a component of the language's lexical structure. Every language has a vocabulary for describing the relationships between a person and their relatives. These are regarded as terms of kinship.

One of the modern approaches to linguistic study that is being actively used right now is the systematic approach. It should be noted, though, that not all language layers can be studied with equal success. When learning the vocabulary of a language, the system approach can be especially difficult and rarely works. The following are the reasons this process is time-consuming and inconvenient: "Very strange vocabulary exists in all languages. Compared to topics related to morphology, phonetics, or syntax, it is more difficult to investigate methodically. Choosing an "oppositional pair of terms" is somewhat conditional because of the lexicon's "openness" and continuous mobility (Fortes, 4).

When analyzing facts of a conventional nature that are equivalent in related and unrelated languages, a comparative-typological approach is applied. It helps researchers investigate speech facts instead of language in a purely terminological sense. Rustamova Sh. Sh. claims that there are a number of factors that affect how difficult it can be to teach a large number of students who have varying attitudes and interests in comparative linguistics. The challenge of planning productive activities is another. Additionally, it can be challenging for teachers to provide every student with an equal opportunity to participate in large classes. More significantly, educators find it difficult to assess students' understanding of kinship terms and give prompt feedback in large class sizes (Rustamova, 92).

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According to Ochilova G. U "Component in the study of lexical-semantic groups the method of analysis was used practically and reasonably. Indeed, some semantic component serves as the basis for distinguishing the semantic field (lexicosemantic group). For example, the word "kinship" with kinship to combine related concepts in one semantic field is used" (Ochilova, 268).

When kinship terms are used in improper meanings, "non-standard" synonymous rows arise between two or more kinship terms. For example, the kinship term aka-brother, meaning elder brother, is synonymous with small father ("father"); with the meaning "grandfather", synonymous with the term bobo/grandfather ("grandfather on the side of the father and on the side of the mother"); the kinship term opa/elder sister with the meaning "mother" is synonymous with the term ona//mother ("mother"); with the meaning "aunt on the side of the father" is synonymous with the term amma//aunt with the meaning "aunt on the mother's side" is synonymous with the term xola - aunt, etc. In such cases, the semantic structure of terms acquires new seme-features that are not characteristic of their own meanings. For example, in the semantic structures of the terms aka/elder brother with the meaning "father", opa/elder sister with the meaning "mother", the attribute "blood parent" appears, etc.

Our study aims to conduct a synchronous-comparative analysis of the terms of kinship between the English and Uzbek languages. As is well known, kinship terms comprise a type of microsystem within each language's vocabulary.

Our study aims to conduct a synchronous-comparative analysis of the terms of kinship between the English and Uzbek languages. As is well known, kinship terms comprise a type of microsystem within each language's vocabulary. 1) kinship terms (ota, o'g'il, qiz, aka//og'a, ini, opa, singil, qarindosh, buva, amaki, jiyan, nevara); 2) kinship terms of postmarital relations (er, xotin, kuyov, kelin, yanga, pochcha, ovsin, kelin oyi, qayin, o'gay); 3) the names of the properties of related relations (kindred children, siblings). I. Ismoilov provides pertinent material from various Turkic languages, including Uzbek, Uighur, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, and Turkmen, during the analysis to support the suggested provisions. The paper said that "... the study of kinship terms in the Uzbek and Uighur languages was of a non-linguistic nature." M.Sh. Saidova, who states that "the study of kinship terms is predominantly ethnographic in nature," concurs with this point of view. Her dissertation "Lexico-semantic analysis of kinship terms in Namangan dialects" developed this thesis. It examined the etymology of these terms and identified factors that contributed to their formation and continued evolution in the Namangan dialects of the Uzbek language.

The study documents the evolution of kinship phrases across time, tracing their phonetic, morphological, and semantic transformations.

Conclusion. Kinship serves as an adaption mechanism. It is referred to in different ways throughout civilizations as a sociocultural invention meant to satisfy the particular needs of a society. Unlike what most of us think, family is not a biological tie but rather one that is established by culture.

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